

The model of quantum entanglement

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Abstract

We establish a model of quantum entanglement and explain the mechanism of quantum entanglement. Quantum entanglement comes from the structural properties of microscopic particles. The correlation of particle structure leads to the entanglement of particles. In fact, there is an interactive structural relationship between particles. The particles are actually large, not as small as the traditional view suggests.

Key word

Quantum entanglement, quantum mechanics, general relativity

Introduction

Quantum entanglement has been proved to be true by experiments. But it is still very mysterious. Two separated particles can express a certain relationship. This obviously makes no sense. We believe that the key to the problem lies in the most basic constituent units of matter. We believe that the most basic constituent unit of matter is different from the traditional view. The traditional view holds that the most basic constituent unit of matter is something very small. But we think it is a very big thing. We call it the T-unit.(1) Its special structure produces quantum entanglement.

1.The traditional view is that large objects are composed of small objects, and small objects are composed of smaller objects. The basic unit of matter is a very small, dense object. Figure 1

fig.1 Particles in traditional view

- 1.The larger the particle radius, the lower the density.
- 2.The smaller the particle radius, the higher the density.
- 3.The basic unit of matter is extremely small, and its density is extremely high.

2.We consider the T-unit as a spherical field with an infinite radius. Its core density is very high, and its peripheral density is low. Figure 2

3.The particles are composed of T-units, so they are also spherical fields with high core density. The radius of a spherical field is infinite. Therefore, the two particles involved in quantum entanglement are actually connected with each other. Figure 3

fig.3 The two particles are actually connected

4.Because of the close relationship between the two particles, it is reasonable for them to influence each other. Simply regard them as two gears, and quantum entanglement is a reasonable result.

Figure 4

fig.4 They interact like two gears

5. The core density of spherical field is high, and the peripheral density is low. Obviously, the interaction between particles is positively related to the field density. In this way, we can explain the quantum entanglement of multiple particles.

Figure 5

fig.5 They interact like a set of gears

Conclusion

1. The basic constituent unit of matter is T-unit, and the radius of T unit is infinite. Therefore, the particle radius is infinite. So, the particles actually touch each other.

- 2.The particles contact each other and cause quantum entanglement.
- 3.Pauli exclusion principle is the same thing as quantum entanglement.
- 4.All substances are interconnected.

Reference

- 1.<https://vixra.org/abs/2004.0650>